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Effect of Audio-Visual Aids on Performance in Business Studies among Secondary School Students in Oredo Local Government, Edo State

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Abstract

The study examined the effects of audiovisual aids on performance in Business Studies among Secondary School Students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The increased low academic performance of Students in this subject area has generated hot quest for investigation on the utilization of audio-visual aids by teachers of this subject. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of this study comprised 758 (400 male and 358 female) Junior Secondary two (JSS11) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in 35 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The study sampled fifty (50), (25 males and 25 females) students from two (2) public Secondary Schools' Students during the 2022/ 2023 academic session local Government Area. A four-point rating scale questionnaire and Business Studies Achievement Performance Test (BSAPT) which were validated and reliability coefficient of 0.78 Was obtained using Kuder Richardson formula 20. Data collected from the study were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions posed, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings include that there is significant difference between audio-visual aids utilization and the academic performance in Business studies' students. And that there is significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area. The study concludes that the students in Business studies in this Oredo Local Government Area are not being taught with adequate audio-visual aids. Hence, it recommended among others that Schools and educational institutions should invest in the acquisition and maintenance of audiovisual equipment and resources.

Keyword: Audio-Visual Aids, Academic Performance, Business Studies

Introduction

The recurrent and worsening low academic performance of students in external examinations as presented by the chief examiner of West African Examination Council (WAEC), in general and particularly the Business Study as a subject has attracted the attention of stakeholders in education. Though other variables that could enhance or inhibit academic performance are being regularly investigated, there are likelihood that the utilization of instructional aids may also be liable for the low understanding of concepts, hence poor academic performance. Traditional teaching approaches, primarily relying on textbooks and lectures, may not always capture the attention and engagement of students effectively. As a result, educators are increasingly turning to audiovisual materials to enhance the teaching and learning experience. According to Nwokedi & Ufodike (2016), the field of education in Nigeria has witnessed significant developments over the years, with an increasing emphasis on innovative teaching methods and the integration of technology in the classroom. The discipline of Business Studies plays a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge and skills necessary for success in the business world. However, the traditional approaches to teaching Business Studies often rely on textbooks and lectures, which may not fully engage students or cater to their diverse learning needs. In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the potential benefits of audiovisual materials in the teaching and learning process.

Audiovisual materials refer to the use of visual and auditory resources, such as videos, presentations, multimedia tools, and interactive technologies, to enhance the educational experience. These materials offer dynamic and interactive means of delivering content, making it more engaging, memorable, and accessible to students. Audio-visual materials arouse the interest of learners and help teachers in explaining the concepts easily and effectively. Lestage in (Job & Opeyemi, 2020), pointed out

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that technology can never replace the human mind, but it can help expand it. It is the duty of the teachers to use audio-visual materials relevant to the lesson and students; wrong use and selection of the teaching materials could be a wastage of time and energy for nothing. Mathew (2013) stated that it is the responsibility of the teacher to use audio-visual materials to make the teaching-learning process effective. Shamsideen (2016) asserted that teaching and learning activities are interesting when audio-visual materials are used effectively and efficiently in a classroom-teaching situation. It is a universal fact that children learn best by observing and copying the behaviors of adults. Sunder in (Okafor, 2018), stated that learning is more effective when sensory experiences are stimulated. Teaching materials stimulate the behaviors of the students toward learning. Sunder in (Okafor, 2018), stated that teaching materials strengthen teaching skills, attract and retain learner's interest and attention and make teaching learning process more interactive and knowledge centered. So, keeping in the mind views of different scholars there is keen need and importance of teaching materials to make the teaching-learning process result-oriented, easy, effective and interesting for both teachers and students; the present investigation is an attempt to ascertain the effectiveness of audio-visual materials in teaching-learning process (Prem, 2018). According to Job & Ado (2019), Resources could aid the understanding of students because it involves the use of cognitive, affective and psychomotor domains. The implication is that resources that best enhance the communication of particular lessons' ideas should be brought into the classroom during the course of teaching such ideas. The use of multimedia is therefore a better attempt at a better application of educational technology in the classroom.

Teaching involves various activities and attempts that are geared toward changing the behaviour of a learner in a specific context. Paul in (Eze & Ojuro, 2020), explained that change could be in attitude, knowledge, idea, skill or appreciation. Effective teaching of any subject will not only stimulate students' interest in the subject but also enhance their achievement in an examination. To achieve effective teaching and learning, there is need for availability and adequate utilization of instructional materials to be adequately available and utilized by teachers as they enable students grasp ideas better. Instructional materials are the different teaching materials or apparatus which a teacher employs to facilitate teaching and achieve stated objectives. Agun in Emeasoba and Igwe (2016) defined instructional materials as those materials which are helpful to teachers and students to maximize learning in various areas. The unique role of instructional materials in classroom teaching and learning is enormous. This means that method of teaching will be grossly incomplete where instructional materials are not utilized. Aransiola in Eze (2021), identified instructional materials for teaching business subjects to include textbooks, manuals, workbooks, magazines, pictures, films, models, simulators and stationeries. They consist of print and non-print items such as kits, textbooks, magazines, newspapers, pictures and recording videos that make the teaching and learning process interesting especially in the teaching of business studies (Effiong & Igiri, 2015). Business Studies is a dynamic subject which prepare students for the challenges of the 21st century by introducing them to the world of business and self-reliance. Business studies is integrated in nature which means that the subject is taught as a single subject with components. It is expository and discovery in nature which enable students to discover those skills and potentials that help individuals in future for life-long education. Hence, Umezulike and Okoye (2013) considered business studies as the key agent of economic and technological development either as a way of developing human capacity, increasing the shield of workforce for modernization, industrialization, and environmental development or as a matter of personal freedom and empowerment of the populace. According to Amoor in (Agun, 2018), business studies play significant role in the economic development of the society by providing knowledge and skills to the learners, thereby, enabling them to adequately impart knowledge into others, and handle sophisticated office technologies and information systems. The goal of business studies is primarily to produce competent, skillful and dynamic business teachers, office administrators and businessmen and women that will effectively compete in the world of work. If these objectives will be achieved, then efforts should be made to provide adequate instructional materials to Nigeria junior secondary schools in teaching of Business Studies and to encourage its effective use.

The use of instructional materials in teaching of business studies is very important because it provides a concrete basis for conceptual thinking, motivates students to learn and captures their imagination if used correctly. Instructional materials provide the teacher with interesting and compelling platforms for conveying information since they motivate learners to learn more (Adekunle, 2018). Furthermore, the teacher is assisted in overcoming physical difficulties that could have hindered his effective presentation of a given topic. According to Akude in (Job & Opeyemi, 2020), the influence of instructional materials in promoting students' academic performance is indisputable. The teaching of business studies in Nigeria secondary school needs to be properly handled. The materials used by teachers to teach and drive home their subject at the primary and secondary school levels of the education system are important in practical classroom interaction to successfully transfer knowledge from teachers to learners. Despite the emphasis placed on the usefulness of instructional materials in the teaching and learning process, most students still find it difficult to cope with the study of business studies. One possible reason for this could be the

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non-utilization of instructional materials that can easily convey the message of the lesson to the learners. Orji in Effiong and Igiri (2015) stated that teaching aid is the guidance of learning activities that a teacher uses to motivate and arouse students to learn. This implies clear that for effective learning to take place, students need to be properly guided by the teacher with concrete materials. According to Bongotons and Onyenwe (2016), one of the pillars of a successful implementation of effective business teacher education is the adequacy and utilization of teaching and learning materials. These materials are in form of facilities and equipment needed to foster skill development and allow for standards and quality in products. Unfortunately, one of the major challenges facing the junior secondary schools and indeed business studies is inadequate teaching and learning resources. Utilization of instructional materials is the act of using and applying the available instructional materials in the actual teaching/learning process. Where resources are supplied for instructional use, teachers are expected to utilize them to support a smooth and meaningful flow of instruction and promote understanding of the content being taught, (Nwabunwanne, in Enekwe, Vero & Osuji, 2020). The teacher who uses instructional materials should be able to manipulate and operate the available units: They should be able to use them to meet the learning needs of the particular learning or group of learners' they are dealing with. This is why Okafor (2013) pointed out that effectiveness of learning materials is determined by the way they are manipulated by teachers or instructors. Instructional materials are in various classes such as audio or aural, visual or audio visual. Audio instructional materials refer to those devices that make use of the sense of hearing only like radio, audio tape recording and television. Visual instructional materials are those devices that appeal to the sense of sight only such as the chalkboard, chart, slide and film strip. An audio-visual instructional material is a combination of devices which appeal to the sense of both hearing and seeing such as television, motion picture and the computer (Isola, 2018). This study focused on the extent of utilization of these instructional materials in teaching and learning of business studies such as projected visual materials, non-projected materials and computer assisted instructional materials. Projected visuals refer to media formats in which still images are projected onto a screen. Such projection is achieved by passing a strong light through transparent film (overhead transparencies, slides, and filmstrips), magnifying the image through a series of lenses, and casting the image onto a reflective surface (Reiser & Dempsey, Job & Opeyemi (2020). Projected visuals are instructional materials that summarize information and ideas through overhead projector, computer images, sound slide sets, multi-image presentations, filmstrips and opaque projections. Patrick in Boor (2016) noted that most students are initially less familiar with projected visuals than they are with flat pictures. They are valuable means of communicating certain information and have generally been found to aid the teacher and the learner by providing visual, audio information. They are aimed at supplementing and improving teaching and learning.

The use of projected media attracts inputs from the teachers and the students; however, they are not intended to end the work of teachers. The use of projected media increases the rate of learning by providing worthwhile experiences for learners. According to Orji in (Nwadike & Ufodike, 2016) projected visuals give instruction a more scientific base through providing a framework for systematic instruction planning. The method required by the teacher to make the teaching of business studies effective demands that the teacher should be very resourceful. Instructional materials are to be used to serve and meet many of education needs if only educators can access and effectively utilize them. Meziobi in Serhat (2021) revealed that the application of projected instructional visuals in teaching has been found to enhance instructions. Today, projected visuals are highly rated worldwide to be of great value in the teaching and learning process. Non projected visuals are those aids which are used without any projection which translate abstract ideas into a more realistic format. They allow instruction to move from verbal representation to a more concrete level. Non-projected learning materials are not technological but are the very basic stuff that has been used in classrooms for years. Like printed and duplicated materials, non-projected media include posters, cartoons, charts, pictures and graphs, and what students produce by themselves can provide powerful visual support for learning abstract ideas. The non-projected media can be presented in the classroom or used as a part of a class activity (Bello, 2015). They are particularly helpful with objectives requiring the identification of people, places or things. The number of a teacher's years of teaching experience can influence the use of instructional media. For instance, personal familiarity with instructional media influences its implementation, Barnard in (Effiong & Igiri 2015&) reported that the acquisition of computer skills is neither smooth nor linear and takes time and aspiration. Barnard further explains that the more experienced a teacher is with any form of instructional media, the more the teacher will appreciate it and implement it practically in the field. Despite the obvious usefulness of instructional materials in the teaching and learning process, most teachers still find it difficult to cope with the teaching of business studies.

The study leaned on constructivist theory of learning, which idea is based on learners being active participants in their learning journey, and knowledge is constructed based on experiences. As events occur, each person reflects on their experience and incorporates the new ideas with their prior knowledge. The theory asserts that Learners develop schemas to organize

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acquired knowledge, and this model was entrenched in learning theories as espoused by Dewey, Piaget, Vygotsky, Gagne, and Bruner. The idea that students actively construct knowledge is central to constructivism, as they add (or build) their new experiences on top of their current foundation of understanding. As stated by Woolfolk in (Job & Opeyemi 2020) “learning is active mental work, not passive reception of teaching”. The theory of constructivism has many elements. These principles outline the theory as a whole and how they affect the learning of the students. The main points are listed below:

1. Knowledge is constructed. Every student begins the learning journey with some preexisting knowledge and then continues to build their understanding on top of that. They will select which pieces of the experience to add, making everyone’s knowledge unique.
2. Learning is a social activity. Interacting with others is vital to constructing knowledge. Group work, discussions, conversations, and interactions are all important to creating understanding. When we reflect on our past experiences, we can see how our relationship with others is directly connected to the information learned.
3. Learning is an active process. Students must actively engage in discussions and activities in order to construct knowledge. It is not possible for students to take on a passive role and retain information. In order to build meaningful ideas, there must be a sensory response.
4. Learning is contextual. Isolation is not the best way to retain information. We learn by forging connections between what we believe and the information we have already. Learning also occurs in the situation within the context of our lives, or alongside the rest of our understanding. We reflect on our lives and classify the new information as it fits into our current perspective.
5. People learn to learn, as they learn. As each student moves through the learning journey, they get better at selecting and organizing information. They are able to better classify ideas and create more meaningful systems of thought. They also begin to recognize that they are learning multiple ideas simultaneously, for example, if they are writing an essay on historical events, they are also learning elements of written grammar. If they are learning about important dates, they are also learning how to chronologically organize important information.
6. Learning exists in the mind. Hands-on activities and physical experience are not enough to retain knowledge. Active engagement and reflection are critical to the learning journey. In order to develop a thorough understanding, students must experience activities mentally as well.
7. Knowledge is personal. Because every person’s perspective is unique, so will be the knowledge gained. Every individual comes into the learning activity with their own experiences and will take away different things as well. The theory of constructivist learning is based entirely around each individual’s own perspective and experiences.
8. Motivation is key to learning. Similar to active participation, motivation is key to making connections and creating understanding. Students cannot learn if they are unwilling to reflect on preexisting knowledge and activate their thought process. It is crucial that educators work to motivate their students to engage in the learning journey.

According to Serhat (2021), it is not enough to simply know the theory of constructivist learning, educators must also know how to implement it in their classrooms, as their goal is to create a welcoming environment that promotes active engagement in learning. In the theory of constructivist learning, instructors act as facilitators, hence, must promote collaboration and adjust their lessons based on the prior level of understanding of the class. Once they identify students’ existing knowledge, instructors must work to grow the understanding in those areas.

There are four key areas that are crucial to the success of a constructivist classroom:

1. The instructor takes on the role of a facilitator instead of a director.
2. There are equal authority and responsibility between the students and the instructor.
3. Learning occurs in small groups.
4. Knowledge is shared between both the students and the instructor.

Constructivism as a learning theory has several educational implications when it comes to the use of audio-visual materials in teaching.

The academic performance of Business Studies’ Students keeps nose-diving despite the various efforts of Governments at all levels emphasizing the importance of education in our society. Perhaps, the teachers of this subject may not have been utilizing Audio-Visual Aids to simplify their teaching. These teachers may hold the notion that the subject is a simple one that requires little or no preparation. To them, teaching Business studies involves merely talking to students about a given topic as may be taken from textbooks or a mere look at some pictures. Business studies teaching requires adequate instructional materials as may be needed in teaching the subject at any level of education. It is, however, worrisome to note that despite its usefulness to the teaching process, Business studies teachers may not have taken full advantage of audiovisual

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aids such that it is inappropriately selected and may not be regularly put to use. Based on the above hindrances, coupled with the fact that students do not retain for long or understand what they are taught without Audio-Visual Aids, the need to investigate the utilization of Audio-Visual Aids in the teaching of Business studies by teachers in junior secondary schools of Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State has become very crucial as none utilization of these instructional aids could demotivate the learners, hence poor academic performance.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To determine the academic performance of students taught Business studies using Audio-Visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching methods in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State
2. To determine the academic performance of Male and Female Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Research Questions:

1. What is the Mean academic performance of Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids and those Exposed to Conventional Teaching Methods in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.
2. What is the Mean Academic Performance of Male and Female Students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between mean academic performance of students taught Business studies using audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area.
2. There is no significant difference between mean academic performance of male and female students taught Business studies using Audio-visual Aids in Oredo Local Government Area.

Methodology:

The design adopted in this study was a descriptive survey. According to Nworgu (2015), a survey research design is the one that aims at collecting data and describing in a systematic manner the characteristics, features or facts about a given population. The study was carried out in Edo State which is made up of 18 Local Government Areas with a total of 300 public secondary schools distributed in three senatorial districts namely, Edo South, Edo Central and Edo North. The Area of the study is Oredo Local Government Area. Oredo LGA functions as one of the 18 LGAs with its headquarters in the town of Benin City. The population of this study comprised 48 Business Studies subject teachers and 758 Junior Secondary Students in 35 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. Random Sampling technique was used to select the schools that formed the sample of the study. The sample for the study was twenty (20) Business Studies teachers from ten (10) public secondary schools and fifty (50) students from two (2) public secondary schools in Oredo LGA. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Application of Audio-Visual Aids in Teaching and Learning of Business Studies (QAAATLBS)" and Business Studies Achievement Test (BSAT). The questionnaire contains forty (40) items and was structured on the basis of research questions on a four-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D), and Strongly Disagreed (SD). The BSAT consists of twenty (20) items of multiple-choice objective tests drawn from past BECE questions.

The Questionnaire on the Application of Audio-Visual Aids in Teaching and Learning of Business Studies (QAAATLBS) and BSAT were subjected to face and content validation by three experts in Business Education. These experts subjected the instruments to rigorous scrutiny in order to ascertain the clarity, relevance, adequacy, and other attributes which a good research instrument should possess. The researchers reconstructed the instruments based on the suggestions of the experts. The BSAT was pilot tested in the school that was part of the population but was not used in the final for the study, and the results were carefully collated and used to determine the reliability coefficient. The split-half reliability for QAAATLBS was 0.78 while that of BSAT is 0.72 which was considered high enough for use. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to the sampled teachers. After 40-50 minutes, all the copies of the questionnaire administered were completely filled and returned. Two schools were used for the treatment. In one of the schools, the researcher taught JSS 1 students Banking using Audio-visual Aids while in the second school, the students were taught without utilizing Audio-visual Aids. A week after the treatment, the BSAT was administered, marked and the scores were carefully recorded for analysis. Mean ratings and standard deviation were used to analyze the data relating to the research questions. The data collected related to the hypothesis were analyzed using arithmetic mean(x), standard deviation (SD) and t-test statistical analysis. The results of the different groups were computed and used in testing the hypotheses. The level of significance adopted for the analysis was $p=0.05$ which

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formed the basis for accepting or rejecting each of the hypothesis. For decision rule, if t-calculated value is greater than the t-critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected (which means significant) and if the t- calculated value is less than the t-critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted (which means not significant).

Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean academic performance of students taught Business studies using Audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area?

Table 1. Mean scores of academic performances of students taught Business Studies using Audio-visual Aids and those exposed to conventional teaching method in Oredo Local Government Area

S/N	The relationship between audio-visual utilization and the academic performance of students	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	Sd.	x_{avr} .	Sd. _{avr}	Decision
1	The integration of audio-visual aids in teaching improves students' academic performance in Business Studies.	10	8	2	0	3.4	0.68			
2	The use of audio-visual aids encourages active participation and involvement of students in the learning process.	7	8	3	2	3.0	0.97	3.46	0.67	Strongly Agree
3	Audio-visual materials make learning Business Studies more enjoyable for students	14	6	0	0	3.7	0.47			
4	Audio-visual aids help students retain information better compared to traditional teaching methods	12	7	1	0	3.6	0.61			
5	The use of audio-visual aids enhances students' motivation to study Business Studies	13	6	1	0	3.6	0.60			

From table 1 above, the average mean response is 3.46 with a Standard Deviation (Sd.) of 0.67. This implies a generally positive effect of audio-visual aids utilization on Business studies' students' academic performance in Oredo Local Government Area.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between audio-visual utilization and the academics performance of Business studies' students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Table 2: t-test analysis on the effect of audio-visual aids utilization and the academic performance of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area

Group	N	Mean(x)	SD	Df.	Tcal	t.crit.	Std. error	Decision
Experimental	25	74.72	5.86					
Control	25	57.76	6.23	48	9.9147	2.021	1.711	Significant
Mean Diff.		16.96						

The result as shown in table 3 reveals that the mean performance scores for the experimental group is 74.72 with a standard deviation of 5.86 while the mean performance scores for the control group is 57.76 with a Standard Deviation (Sd.) of 6.23. The mean difference of the scores of experimental and control groups is 16.96. The result of the hypothesis 1 in the table 3 also

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indicates that t-calculated value of 9.9147 is greater than that of the t-critical value of 2.021. Therefore, the null hypothesis 1 is not accepted. This implies that there is significant effect of audio-visual aids utilization and the academics performance of Business studies' students in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question 2.

What is the difference in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo LGA taught with audio-visual instructional material?

Table 3: Mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo LGA taught with audio-visual instructional material

S/N	Difference between the academic performance of male and female students taught with audio-visual instructional materials	SA	A	D	SD	X	Sd.	$x_{avr.}$	Sd_{avr}	Decision
1	I believe that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both male and female students.	14	5	1	0	3.7	0.59			
2	Audio-visual presentations facilitate a better understanding of subject content for male students.	12	8	0	0	3.6	0.50			
3	Audio-visual presentations facilitate a better understanding of subject content for female students.	10	6	4	0	3.3	0.80	3.1	0.90	Agree
4	Male students benefit more from the use of audio-visual instructional material compared to female students.	8	1	6	5	2.6	1.27			
5	Female students benefit more from the use of audio-visual instructional material compared to male students.	6	2	3	9	2.3	1.33			

Table 3 reveals that the average mean response is 3.1 with a standard deviation (Sd.) of 0.90. This implied that there are differences in the academic performance of Male and Female students in Oredo Local Government Area taught with audio-visual aids. However, while there is general agreement that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both genders and that they facilitate a better understanding for male students, there is more variability in opinions about their effect on female students' understanding.

Hypothesis 2.

There is no significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

Table4. t-test analysis of academic performance of Male and Female Business studies' students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area

Gender	N	Mean(x)	SD	Df.	$t_{cal.}$	$t_{crit.}$	Decision
Male	10	70.20	5.69				
Female	15	77.23	3.66	23	4.0287	2.019	Significant

The result of hypothesis 2 in the table 4 indicates that the t-calculated value of 4.0287 is greater than that of the t-critical value of 2.019. Therefore, the null hypothesis 2 is not accepted. This implies that there is significant mean difference in the academic performance of Male and Female Business studies' students taught with audio-visual aids in Oredo Local Government Area at 0.05 level of significance.

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Discussion of Findings

This study was carried out with the aim to determine the effect of audio-visuals aids utilization in teaching and learning of Business Studies in public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State. The data from table 1 indicates a generally positive effect of audio-visual utilization and the academic performance of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government area. Which means integrating audio-visual aids improves academic performance, encourages active participation, makes learning enjoyable, helps retain information, and enhances motivation to study. The mean scores for each point support this positive perception. The findings suggest that audio-visual utilization is associated with positive effect of learning outcomes and experiences among Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area. This finding agrees with Enekwe, Vero & Osuji (2020), on their study – the challenges and possible solution to the utilization of audio-visual materials in teaching social studies in upper basic schools in Udi educational zone, Enugu. They submitted among others that students should be involved in the improvisation and use of audio-visual materials, as they learn more from what they do. It also validates the study of Eze & Ojuro (2020) on their study- to determine the utilization of instructional materials in teaching and learning of Business studies in secondary schools in Anambra State. The study affirmed that utilization of instructional materials by teachers should help students acquire skills. Effiong & Igiri (2015) also agreed that teaching aids is the guidance of learning activities.

The data from table 2 reveals varying effect on the academic performance of male and female students in Oredo Local Government Area taught with audio-visual instructional aids. While there is general observation that audio-visual aids are equally beneficial for both genders and that they facilitate a better understanding for male students, there is more variability in opinions about their impact on female students' understanding. Additionally, opinions are divided regarding which gender benefits more from the use of audio-visual aids, (Mathew, 2013, Agun, 2016, Nwakedi & Ufodike, 2016, and Serhat, 2021). Overall, the findings suggest that perceptions of the impact of audio-visual instructional material on gender-specific academic performance are mixed, with no clear consensus on whether one gender benefits more than the other. This indicates a need for further investigation and research to better understand the relationship between gender, audio-visual utilization, and academic performance in the context of Business Studies students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Conclusion

The study's results indicate a positive association between the use of audio-visual materials and the academic performance of Business Studies students. It was evident that integrating audio-visual materials enhances understanding, engagement, motivation, and retention of complex concepts. The analysis of gender-based differences in academic performance showed that while both male and female students benefit from the use of audiovisual materials, there are variations in the extent of benefit. This suggests the importance of considering gender-specific learning preferences and needs when designing instructional strategies involving audiovisual aids. Furthermore, the statistical analysis supported the rejection of the null hypotheses, confirming that there is a significant relationship between audio-visual aids utilization and academic performance, as well as a significant mean difference in the academic performance of male and female Business Studies students taught with audio-visual aids.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the present study, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Teachers should integrate audio-visual materials in their teaching in order to enhance understanding, engagement, motivation, and retention of complex concepts.
2. Teachers should consider gender-specific learning preferences and needs when designing instructional strategies involving audiovisual aids.

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